

**INTERFACIAL STRENGTH OF AN ELECTROMAGNETICALLY
CURED GLASS \ EPOXY COMPOSITE**

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ABSTRACT

Electromagnetic radiation curing of thermoset composite has been shown to achieve comparable and even higher strengths and stiffness than conventional thermal curing. This paper examines the fundamental basis for the attainment of these values by measuring the matrix-fiber interfacial shear strength. A direct but simple method was used to determine the interfacial shear strength, by using a double lap shear joint under a compression load to measure the shear strength. Results indicate that the interfacial strength achieved for different radiation power ratings exceeded the strengths obtained for thermal curing. At higher power ratings, indication of material thermal degradation were present, but were minimized by using an intermittent radiation approach.

KEYWORDS: matrix, epoxy; interface; electromagnetic; degradation

INTRODUCTION

Recent work in the curing of thermoset composites have extended to electromagnetic curing processes [1-3], the advantage over conventional thermal curing being the a significantly shorter total cure time as well as consistency in the degree of cure. In some cases, an increase in the elastic modulus was found, but this has been accompanied by a significant decrease in the tensile strength [1]. In another work, however, both the flexural modulus and the flexural strength of the electromagnetically cured samples were higher than comparable thermally cured samples [2,3]. One possibility for the discrepancy could be due to the different methods used in the processing of the samples [4,5].

It is commonly known that in the case of a low strength matrix - high strength fibre system such as the epoxy / fibre glass system used, the load is taken mainly by the fibre network, and the intrinsic strength of the matrix does not significantly affect the composite strength. However, the more fundamental criteria determining the composite

strength is the fibre-matrix interfacial strength. Provided the latter is strong enough to transfer the stress up to the point of the fibre failure strength, the composite can achieve the maximum possible failure strength. This is particularly so for shear and compressively loaded components [6]. Therefore, the possible discrepancy in the cured strength of composite samples which are differently processed could be explained by the fact that both the thermal and the electromagnetically cured processes resulted in differing interfacial strengths being achieved. It is therefore logical to investigate the strength of the interface for a microwave cured composite, which should give an objective physical basis for predicting if a high composite failure strength can be achieved. This forms the basis of this report.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

For this project, a direct but simple method was used to determine the interfacial shear strength. A double lap shear joint under a compression load was used to measure the shear strength. However, this can be considered to be equivalent to the interfacial strength, since joint failure were dominantly adhesive by nature. The use of a compressive load was also because of the particular influence of the interfacial strength on the composite strength. In order to ensure purely compressive stresses, biaxial stresses induced by misalignment were minimized by using thick glass pieces (5 mm), with the end edges finished by precision diamond grinding. All glass pieces measured 50 mm by 25 mm by 5 mm, cut out from a single float glass Silica E-glass panel. To achieve better horizontal alignment of the specimen edges and the compressive loading jig, elastomer inserts were placed between the hard glass edges and loading jig on both the top and bottom ends. The epoxy inter-layer was kept consistent through the use of a mylar insert between the glass pieces during application of the epoxy. This is important since it ensured that the specimens so processed were consistent. In order to closely simulate the curing cycle during industrial operations, the specimens were thermally cured using a typical industrial cure cycle given in an earlier paper [5]. For specimens that were electromagnetically cured, a 2.45 GHz microwave magnetron was used with a wave guide design providing an effectively constant (when empty) electric field in a multimode cavity measuring 200 mm by 200 mm by 200 mm, giving an effective power range of 0 - 500 W. All specimens were individually radiated to ensure they were radiated under identical conditions. Definition and calibration of the radiation power is given elsewhere [2]. To ensure statistical significance, experimental data indicated are all averaged readings from at least 3 identical specimens. To avoid cluttering, standard deviation markers have not been placed in the figures shown. However, the deviations obtained were within the range of about 0.8 - 2.1 MPa.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 shows the interfacial strength values for different radiation time at a power rating of 175 W. Maximum interfacial strength was achieved in a relatively short time of less than 20 min, resulting in a maximum interfacial strength of almost 20 MPa. This is higher than the value of 15 MPa obtained for specimens thermally cured at 120 °C for 12 h, indicated in the same figure. Figure 2 indicates the results at 275 W. The maximum strength was achieved both in a shorter time, and for a higher value at about 26 MPa. However, continuous radiation beyond 25 min seemed to drastically reduce the strength. Similar results were obtained at 400 W, except that the degradation commenced at a still shorter time of after 20 min. Further continuous radiation did not result in any strength. Specimens which so resulted in such a strength degradation also displayed discoloration typical of material thermal degradation. For the 400 W, some specimens had evidences of the epoxy having charred into a black discoloration. Evidently, at this power rating and radiation time, the heating rate and temperature was sufficiently high to degrade the material. This can occur if before full conversion into a fully cross-linked material could be effected, vitrification had occurred. Close to and at the point of vitrification, the heat loss factor increases rapidly, resulting in a highly exothermic effect. The resulting surge in temperature could then have charred the unconverted portion of the component. Alternatively, it is possible that the material temperature excessively exceeded the glass transition temperature for a significant time to result in the degradation.

Such a thermal degradation can be minimized during electromagnetic curing since the curing process is by radiation, and can be instantaneously turned on and off, and the operation can be done at room or even lower temperatures. To ascertain that the drop in the interfacial strength was due to degradation by accumulated heat generated by the heat loss factor, specimens were intermittently radiated at 400 W for 5 and 10 min respectively, left to cool for 15 min, and then radiated again for the same time etc. Temperature readings indicate that 15 min was sufficient in all case to cool the specimens to the microwave ambient temperature. Figure 3 indicate the results for the 400 W power rating, intermittently cured using 5 min and 10 min radiation time with alternating 15 min cooling time. No sudden drop in the strength is now observed. The maximum strength for 10 min intermittent curing achieved a significantly higher strength at 24 MPa, than for the 5 min intermittent curing at 16 MPa. The results thus provide an objective basis for predicting that the composite failure strength should be higher in microwave cured than thermally cured specimens, provided the process is optimized to avoid overheating.

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